

Uranyl Ion Complexes with Potentially Tridentate Amino Acids

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Complexation of uranyl ion by potentially tridentate amino acids has been investigated. In serine and threonine, the OH group is not in a spatially favoured position for tridentate coordination. The possibility of bidentate coordination using carboxyl and hydroxo groups has been examined by polarography and potentiometry. The results indicate that serine and threonine react with uranyl using the carboxyl function only. In the case of 4-amino-3-hydroxybutyric acid, the shift in $E_{1/2}$ for the reduction of the complex relative to the non-chelated one is significant and suggests chelation. Polarographic evidence indicates chelation through the unionized hydroxyl. The amino group is not involved in complexation.

IN the potentially tridentate hydroxy amino acids, serine, threonine and 4-amino-3-hydroxybutyric acid, the three functional groups, namely, carboxyl, hydroxy and amino, differ widely in their basicities and offer a choice of relatively 'hard', 'intermediate' and 'soft' basic donor sites. Further, the hydroxy group can coordinate with or without deprotonation. In serine and threonine, the positions of the three donor groups render them sterically unfavourable for effective tridentate coordination. In such cases the metal can choose either carboxyl and amino groups or amino and hydroxy groups to form five-membered ring chelates. In the potentially tridentate 4-amino-3-hydroxybutyric acid, the amino group is away on the 4th carbon atom making it possible to form two chelate rings, one involving the carboxyl and hydroxy groups and the other involving the hydroxy and amino groups. The present set of ligands were chosen for determining the nature of binding in the complexes with uranyl ion and also the relative donor abilities of the $-COOH$, $-OH$ and $-NH_2$ groups.

Experimental

Materials: Uranyl perchlorate was prepared from uranyl nitrate (A.R., B.D.H.) by the standard procedure². It was assayed by the Jone's reductor method³ for uranyl content and by cation exchange method⁴ for free acid. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide was used in the titrations. The ligand acids (either E. Merck or Fluka) were used as such. Sodium perchlorate was used to maintain the ionic strength at 0.1 M.

Potentiometry: An ECIL digital pH meter with a separate glass and calomel electrode assembly and with an accuracy of ± 0.01 pH unit was used for pH titrations. It was standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer. All titrations were

carried out in a thermostated cell at $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The cell was suitably protected from photochemical reaction of uranyl ion by black paper. The acidity constants of the acid and basic functions of the amino acids were determined by the method of Albert⁵.

Polarography: The effect of varying pH on the $E_{1/2}$ of uranyl complexes at constant concentration of the ligand was investigated by measuring the $E_{1/2}$ values for uranyl solutions (8×10^{-4} M) at a constant ionic strength ($NaClO_4$, 0.1 M) at $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The polarograms were recorded on an automatic Metrimplex, type OH 105 Universal polarograph with a three electrode set up. The electrode characteristics were $h=40.0$ cm, $t=3.85$ sec and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6}=4.25$ $mg^{2/3} sec^{-1/2}$. The $E_{1/2}$ values were measured to an accuracy of ± 0.5 mV and were reproducible to ± 1 mV. The reversibility of each system studied was checked by logarithmic analysis or by measuring the difference in $E_{1/4} - E_{3/4}$ values. The reduction of UO_2^{2+} was found to be a reversible one electron process with an $E_{1/2}$ of -0.175 V vs SCE.

Conductometry: The maximum number of ligand molecules coordinated to UO_2^{2+} was determined by conductometric titrations of the sodium salts of the ligands against uranyl perchlorate using a direct reading Toshniwal Conductivity Analyser, type L 01.06.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometry: The pH titration curves of the amino acid-metal mixtures (1:1 or higher ratios) are displaced, beginning at a lower pH value relative to that of the ligand alone under identical conditions. This clearly shows that complexation occurs. In all the cases, an inflection occurs at 'one mole of base

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per one mole of ligand followed by a buffer region. Precipitation was observed in the neighbourhood of pH 5.4 irrespective of the metal-ligand ratio. The buffer region indicates hydrolysis of the complex beyond pH 3.5. This is clear from the plot of $Z/2$ vs $(\log T_m + 2pH)$ for titrations of metal salt + perchloric acid vs alkali in presence as well as in absence of the ligand. The $Z/2$ values calculated for both the titrations were found to be similar leading to the conclusion that the reaction in the buffer region is similar, namely, hydrolysis.

Uranyl-L-serine and -L-threonine systems : The ligands are present as protonated species in presence of excess perchloric acid. There are thus three replaceable protons, on the carboxyl, the hydroxy and the amino groups. Of these, the proton on the carboxyl is the more acidic one and will be neutralized first. Since the inflection occurs below pH 3.5 it is reasonable to infer that the carboxyl group gets deprotonated and coordinated to the metal ion. The deprotonation of amino and the hydroxy groups is known to occur at a much higher pH. The overall inference then is that only the carboxyl oxygen interacts with the metal ion and there is no chelation.

Uranyl-4-amino-3-hydroxybutyric acid system : The titration curves indicate complexation of a higher degree than with serine and threonine. The inflection is noted at one mole of alkali per mole of ligand indicating that the carboxyl group alone is deprotonated. However, the ligand forms 1:2 complex as indicated from the \bar{n} values. The $\log K_{ML}$ and $\log K_{ML_2}$ values of 2.77 and 1.90, respectively were calculated using the Irving and Rossotti equation⁷ below the hydrolysis region. The $\log \beta_{ML_2}$ value of 4.67 obtained in the present study is in order with the values reported⁸ for complexes of 2-hydroxy- and 3-hydroxy-butyric acids (4.99 and 4.10, respectively) indicating participation of the hydroxy group in coordination.

Polarography :

Uranyl-L-serine and -L-threonine systems : The variation of $E_{1/2}$ as a function of pH was investigated between pH 1.8 and 4.2. The $E_{1/2}$ vs pH diagram (Fig. 1) shows breaks at pH 2.4 corresponding to the deprotonation of the carboxyl group. Below pH 1.8 the $E_{1/2}$ values were independent of pH with a constant value of -0.175 V (vs SCE) and the same as for the aquo ion, indicating that complexation did not occur. Beyond pH 4.2 the reduction tended towards irreversibility possibly due to hydrolysis. In the region $pH > pK_{COOH}$, the $E_{1/2}$ values were independent of pH upto about pH 4 in both the systems. With the experimental pH below the $pK_{NH_3^+}$ of the amino acid concerned, the amino group, if involved in coordination, would get protonated at the electrode surface on liberation when the complex undergoes polarographic reduction. No such protonation was indicated from the experimental results. It is therefore inferred that the amino nitrogen is not involved in coordination with the metal. Moreover, the magnitude of

the shift in $E_{1/2}$ values is comparable to that of the α -amino acid complexes⁹, indicating that the hydroxy group also is not involved in coordination and that the uranyl forms only simple carboxylate complexes with these ligands.

Fig. 1. Variation of $E_{1/2}$ with pH in uranyl-amino acid complexes.

1. L-Serinate, 2. L-Threoninate, 3. 4-Amino-3-hydroxybutyrate and 4. 3-Hydroxybutyrate.

The number of ligand molecules coordinated to the uranyl ion was determined by the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log HL$ ¹⁰ in conjunction with conductometric titrations. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log HL$ for both serinate and threoninate complexes gave a $(p-q)$ value of 2 (where p and q are the number of ligands attached to the metal in the oxidized and reduced forms, respectively). The absolute value of p as determined by conductometry was found to be 2 for both the complexes. Thus, it is possible to express the reduction at d.m.e. at $pH > pK_{COOH}$ as

The stability constants of the complex species were calculated by Lingane equation.

Uranyl-4-amino-3-hydroxybutyric acid system : The $E_{1/2}$ vs pH relationship was investigated in the pH region between 1.8 and 5.2 (Fig. 1). The studies indicated that complexation did not occur below pH 1.8 and the polarograms tended towards irreversibility at pH above 5.2. The $E_{1/2}$ vs pH diagram shows a break at pH 3.85 corresponding to the deprotonation of the carboxyl group ($pK_{COOH} = 3.91$). Upto pH 3.85 only one proton per metal atom is involved in the electrode reaction indicating the deprotonation of the carboxyl group only on complexation. At $pH > pK_{COOH}$ the $E_{1/2}$ vs pH diagram does not indicate further participation of protons in the electrode reduction indicating that the amino group and the hydroxy group are not deprotonated.

Since NH_3^+ group cannot coordinate without deprotonation, the coordination of the amino group is ruled out. However, the very large shift of nearly 0.15 V in the $E_{1/2}$ values clearly indicates the existence of a chelate complex. It is inferred that the hydroxy group is involved in coordination without ionization forming a six-membered chelate.

In order to confirm the involvement of unionized hydroxy group in coordination, the variation of $E_{1/2}$ as a function of pH was investigated in the case of uranyl-3-hydroxybutyrate complex. The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH for both the complexes are similar, showing breaks at pH corresponding to the pK_{COOH} , and also have comparable $\Delta E_{1/2}$ values. This indicates the similarity in the nature of coordination sites in these two complexes.

Conclusions : The magnitude of $\Delta E_{1/2}$ values for serinate and threoninate complexes are similar to other α -amino acid complexes indicating absence of chelation. On the other hand in uranyl-4-amino-3-hydroxybutyrate complex, the $\Delta E_{1/2}$ as well as log K_{ML} and log K_{ML_2} values indicate chelation

through unionized hydroxy group. Thus, the relative coordinating abilities of the donor groups towards uranyl ion seem to be in the order $\text{COOH} > \text{OH} > \text{NH}_2$. This order is in agreement with the 'hard acid' nature of uranyl ion.

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